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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHAYA Tbearing USN6SU20CV001 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKASH Rbearing USN6SU20CV002 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKSHAY PRASAD bearing USN6SU20CV003 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJANA MARIA ALLELUIA bearing USN6SU20CV004 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARCHANA K Sbearing USN6SU20CV005 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARMAINbearing USN6SU20CV006 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARYA UDAYAN bearing USN6SU20CV007 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms BASILICA MARIYANA D Sbearing USN6SU20CV008 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms BHAVYASREE Mbearing USN6SU20CV009 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEVI NANDANA B bearing USN6SU20CV010 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DHANISHA PERVIN K Pbearing USN6SU20CV011 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DHILSHA Mbearing USN6SU20CV012 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA FAHMIDA C Hbearing USN6SU20CV013 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms H MANASA RAVINDRA bearing USN6SU20CV014 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HALEEMA ASHIQ bearing USN6SU20CV015 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HRITHIK MURALI bearing USN6SU20CV016 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms IBRAHIM ASHIQ bearing USN6SU20CV017 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JISHNA E Pbearing USN6SU20CV018 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JULIA SHAJI bearing USN6SU20CV019 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MANYA Pbearing USN6SU20CV020 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUBASIR ZAMIL Mbearing USN6SU20CV021 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIHARIKA E Gbearing USN6SU20CV022 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIYAS T Bbearing USN6SU20CV023 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RUFSA NA C K bearing USN6SU20CV024 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANDRA V Tbearing USN6SU20CV025 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHIVANI S SAMAGA bearing USN6SU20CV026 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREYA AJITHAN bearing USN6SU20CV027 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms TINCY K JOSE bearing USN6SU20CV028 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms TINCY KOSHY bearing USN6SU20CV029 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHNUPRIYA J Vbearing USN6SU20CV030 has completed his/her internship at Apollo Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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